

Finding Patterns in Productive Failure Steps? An Explorative Case Study in a Teaching Learning Lab for Computer Science

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Abstract. Teaching *algorithmic thinking* is a core task of education in the 21st century. The *productive failure* approach is not yet widely used in computer science, but promising insights in better understanding learning processes in the process of acquiring *algorithmic thinking*. A calliope workshop is designed and implemented to identify N = 13 learner's patterns of *productive failure* steps in students in an exploratory qualitative case study. *Productive failure* patterns will then serve in a subsequent study for training student teachers in formative assessment. The results of this exploratory case study provide preliminary indications of how learning and teaching workshops on *algorithmic thinking* can be designed.

Keywords: Algorithmic Thinking · productive failure · Computational Thinking.

1 Introduction

In order to become an empowered citizen in our rapidly digitizing world, it is of great importance to teach students digital literacy according to, and thus especially *computational thinking* (CT) ([1]). For this to succeed, pedagogical approaches are needed that teach students CT, especially *algorithmic thinking* (AT) as a part of CT ([13]), for us the definition of AT steps according to [11] is crucial. An approach that has already been successfully tested in mathematics is *productive failure* (PF) [3], which belongs to the category PS-I (first problem solving then instruction) according to [5]. The theory states that students learn the content better when they first problem solve (PS) and then receive instruction (I). As an example of a PS-I approach, the approach of [3] and [6] includes four interdependent steps: (a) *activating and differentiating prior knowledge related to the target concepts*, (b) *attending to critical conceptual features of the target concepts*, (c) *explaining and elaborating these features*, and (d) *organizing and merging the critical conceptual features into the target concepts*. In the field of CS education, the approach is not very common yet, only [12] has presented it so far. Therefore, this study has the approach, in a first research step, to

analyze the steps of students who are taught AT using a developed workshop designed according to the principles of PF, and thus possibly identify typical PF patterns for CS education. This data will then be used to train student teachers in our CS Teaching and Learning Lab (TLL) to recognize PF and thus better train formative assessment of students. Overall, this is an exciting new area of research in CS education, which is presented here as a first step using the exploratory study conducted. Our research questions are: **RQ1: What kind of productive failures can be identified during the process of acquiring algorithmic thinking?** **RQ2: To what extent can patterns of productive failures be identified?**

2 Methods

The research question is operationalized through an exploratory single case study [14] that follows a qualitative approach, collecting and analyzing qualitative, triangulated data. Students’ programmed codes were captured at several points during the collaborative group work phases as students worked on the problem-based tasks. We are analyzing the qualitative through qualitative content analysis [7] and developed the following coding scheme to better understand the *productive failures* that were made and to better capture how pre-service teachers identified and categorized them.

Setting and Participants The sample is N=13 high school students, ages 13-14. They participated in a 90-minute workshop. The content was to program a counter step using block-based programming and the calliope. The students’ prior knowledge was programming with Scratch (sequences, loops, conditions, variables). We conducted the Calliope workshop taking into account research-based practices ([9]) to ensure that the workshop was implemented as designed. We considered [10] *treatment fidelity* categories.

Material: Workshop Design We developed a workshop (fig. 1) following [11]’s AT steps and PF [3, 4]’s design principles. Students solved a problem using Calliopes and block-based language. The workshop consisted of 3 phases: Problem Solving, Instruction, and Final Problem Solving (Fig. 1). In the Problem Solving phase, students work independently and individually, but have the opportunity to elaborate and explain at any time. In the instructional phase, different approaches, including failed ones, are presented and compared, and the problem is finally clarified with all the necessary content so that

Fig. 1. Workshop design according to the principles of *productive failure* according to [3], [4] and the *algorithmic thinking* steps according to [11]

each student can create his or her individual solution in the final phase. The problem is challenging but not frustrating.

Instruments and Analysis The students' steps were videotaped on the computer to identify and qualitatively assess the steps in the learning process, especially the steps where PF occurs. In addition, the entire intervention was videotaped so that the students' presentations could be qualitatively assessed. Students worked through the AT steps using a paper-pencil worksheet and the block-based programming language makeBlock. Both the worksheets and the programs created were recorded. The collected qualitative data will be analyzed using a reductive qualitative content analysis according to the interpretive paradigm of [7], using a developed category system based on the categories of [8] adopted by [2] to identify PF patterns.

3 Results and Summary

In our initial analysis of the data, we analyzed the first phase of the workshop, the PS step before instruction, to identify PF. For this purpose, we evaluated the individual video recordings in combination with the created programs. The results show that the most frequently assigned category was Problem Solving (77 out of a total of 221). Orientation (55) and Criteria Development (40). Problem Analysis (21) and Problem Evaluation (27) were less frequent and Problem Critique appeared only once. Additionally we have categorized a total of 15 PFs (RQ1), 7 of which were in the solution development phase (logic errors, flow control errors, number representation errors), 3 in the criteria development phase, and 4 in the orientation phase (e.g., incorrectly selected physical elements or LED display errors). Due to the small number of PFs found, no valid patterns can be identified at this time (RQ2).

This case study is limited in several ways that need to be addressed in future work. First, it included only a small sample, and second, it did not examine the level of AT of the learners at the individual level. Of course, these two aspects could be the reason why only a few PFs could be found. Therefore, in a subsequent study, care should be taken to make the tasks even more open and/or to select a more heterogeneous, larger learning group. The problem solving process in the AT steps can be seen well in the categories, although Problem Analysis and Problem Evaluation are somewhat underrepresented, so that the basic approach in the AT steps according to [11] in combination with PF should be pursued further. In the next step, we will collect more student data and further analyze the data. In addition, we will study several workshops using the principle of PF. This data will be the basis for training students in our CS TLL to recognize PF and thus better train students' formative assessment. In particular, the relationship to misconceptions needs to be explored, as [15] or semantic errors in learning text-based languages are also found in PF steps of block-based

programming. Overall, there are interesting connections to different CS research approaches to be explored.

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